

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ҲУҚУҚНИ МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШ
АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**“Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасида
глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар:
муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусидаги халқаро
конференция материаллари
Т Ў П Л А М И
II-жилд**

**“Глобальные вызовы и угрозы в сфере
правоохранительной деятельности:
проблемы и решения” материалы
международной конференции
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Тўпламда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси ташкил этилганлигининг икки йиллиги муносабати билан бўлиб ўтган “Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасидаги глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусида халқаро конференция материаллари ўрин олган. Унда ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш соҳасидаги таҳдидлар, жумладан коррупция, жиноий маблағларни қонунийлаштириш, терроризмни молиялаштиришга қарши курашишда янги чақириқ ва тенденциялар, тергов фаолиятида рақамли криминалистиканинг аҳамияти, ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш соҳасида фан ва таълим, сунъий интеллектни қўллаш, одам савдоси билан боғлиқ жиноятларни тергов қилиш устидан прокурор назорати самарадорлигини ошириш масалалари юзасидан илмий ва амалий тажриба, фикрлар алмашинувини ўз ичига олади.

Тўплам фан ва таълим соҳасини бошқаришга ваколатли давлат органлари, юридик фан ва ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиёти билан боғлиқ хорижий давлатларнинг етук олимлари, мутасадди ташкилотлар ходимлари, Ўзбекистон Республикасининг юридик фанлар соҳасида кўзга кўринган етук олимлари, профессор-ўқитувчилар, мустақил изланувчилар, докторантлар, магистрлар бошқа ёш олимларнинг мақола ва тезислари баён этилган.

Мазкур тўпламга киритилган материалларнинг мазмуни, ундаги статистик ва бошқа маълумотлар, меъёрий ҳужжатлар санасининг тўғрилигига ҳамда танқидий фикр-мулоҳазаларга муаллифларнинг шахсан ўзлари масъулдирлар.

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ENSURING THE RIGHTS OF PERSONS UNDER CRIMINAL PROSECUTION AND PARTICIPANTS IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS

***Abstract.** Ensuring the security of the rights of persons under criminal prosecution is one of the most pressing issues in modern criminal proceedings. This article presents a legal scientific analysis of the fact that an effective system of protection of all participants in the criminal process should realize human rights and legitimate interests as the highest value. Also, the article provides a comparative legal analysis of foreign practices on ensuring the safety of participants in criminal proceedings.*

***Key words:** criminal prosecution, criminal process, witness, court, trial, security, law, participants, international norms.*

By analyzing the legislation of some CIS countries and states that are part of the Anglo-Saxon and Roman-Germanic legal systems, we can analyze the gaps in our national criminal procedural legislation and the specifics and some differences between institutions by studying the legislation of foreign countries related to ensuring the rights of persons under criminal prosecution.

Rights of persons under criminal prosecution ensuring the security of the criminal justice system is one of the most pressing issues in modern criminal proceedings.

Russian lawyer Y.V.Paukova said that protecting the participants of criminal proceedings from various criminal threats has become one of the global problems today, because according to world statistics, every fourth witness refuses to testify in court¹.

It should be noted that this particular issue is the most important not only at the preliminary investigation stage, but also at the trial stage of the criminal process. At the same time, it is impossible to effectively develop a modern state

¹ Паукова Ю.В. Законодательство в сфере государственной защиты потерпевших, свидетелей и иных участников уголовного судопроизводства // Вестник российской правовой академии. 2005. № 4. С. 66.

without taking into account global trends, accumulated experience, and respect for universally recognized human rights and freedoms.

The first international legal document related to ensuring the safety of participants in criminal proceedings is the UN Caracas Declaration of December 15, 1980, adopted within the framework of the VI UN Congress¹. This document put forward the ideological principles of the need for states members of the world community to form a mechanism that guarantees the equality of all before the law without any discrimination, the effectiveness of the exercise of the right of defense of the accused, the speedy and fair implementation of justice, and the right to security of everyone. In addition, it urged all participating states to reflect these ideas in their national legal systems. Based on the ideas expressed in the generally recognized norms of international law, the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment was adopted on December 10, 1984². In this document, the participating states are called to take necessary measures³ against intimidation, coercion and harassment of the participants of the court proceedings and to strengthen international cooperation in this regard, with particular attention to the adoption and implementation of programs related to ensuring the safety of the participants of the court proceedings and, in necessary cases, their family members, close relatives and persons close to them (Article 24).

Similar provisions were adopted in the UN Convention against Corruption, adopted in New York on October 31, 2003⁴. Article 32 of this Convention, entitled "Protection of victims, witnesses and experts," recommends that each State Party take appropriate measures in accordance with its domestic legal system and within its capabilities.

It should be noted that the additional protocols establishing mechanisms to ensure the appropriate legal status of migrants and victims of trafficking do not contain such provisions. However,⁵ Article 6, paragraph 3 of the Convention recommends that each State take measures to ensure the safety of migrants and victims of trafficking, namely, to recognize as aggravating circumstances in its

¹ Утверждена Резолюцией 35/171, принятой на 96-ом пленарном заседании Генеральной Ассамблеи ООН // Сборник стандартов и норм организации объединенных наций в области предупреждения преступности и уголовного правосудия. Нью-Йорк, 1992. С. 15-16.

² Ўзбекистон Республикаси мазкур Конвенцияга Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий Мажлисининг 1995 йил 31 августдаги 130-I-сонли «1984 йил 10 декабрдаги Қийноқларга солишга ва муомалада бўлиш ва жазолашнинг бошқа шафқатсиз, ғайриинсоний ёки кадр-қимматни таҳқирловчи турларига қарши конвенцияга қўшилиш ҳақида»ги қарорига мувофиқ қўшилган.

³ Конвенция Организации Объединенных Наций против транснациональной организованной преступности. <https://lex.uz/docs/1304112>

⁴ Конвенция против транснациональной организованной преступности (Заклучена в г. Нью-Йорке 15 ноября 2000 г.)

⁵ Protocol against the illegal importation of migrants by land, sea and air, complementary to the United National Convention against transnational organized crime. Adopted resolution 55/25 of the General Assembly in November 2000.

national legislation crimes committed intentionally or with the intention of obtaining material or other benefits.

An effective system of protection of all participants in the criminal process not only ensures the realization of human rights and legitimate interests as the highest value, but also serves the implementation of the main tasks of justice. The creation of a comprehensive system of institutions and mechanisms guaranteeing state protection of this category of persons is one of the achievements of the legislation of many developed countries. Developed countries have been supporting these protective measures in their legal systems for several decades.

It should be noted that international norms shape the legal systems of a particular state, the characteristic features, characteristics, areas, functions, principles and legal institutions of law. Today, the Anglo-Saxon and Roman-Germanic legal systems, which are among the modern legal systems, are part of the legal systems of many states. For example, while deduction (reliance on general specific conclusions) dominates in the Roman-Germanic legal system, in the Anglo-Saxon legal system the consideration of the case on its merits is mainly carried out by representatives of the public under the guidance of a professional judge¹. Also, among the sources of Anglo-Saxon law, judicial precedent prevails, and the content of the law is complex and casuistic.

According to Russian lawyer S.L. Budylin, the rules for assessing evidence in Anglo-Saxon and Roman-Germanic jurisdictions differ significantly. The Anglo-Saxons establish objective standards of proof based on the nature of the case. In countries that are part of the Roman-Germanic legal system, the assessment is based on whether the fact corresponds to the truth or not. Also, in this system, a verdict is made based on the judge's "inner confidence", that is, subjective principles play a large role. In this regard, the Roman-Germanic legal system has a significant advantage over other legal systems in determining the truth².

The US legal system is also based on the principles of British common law. For example, US judges, based on information received about the characteristics of organized criminal groups (persons capable of exerting pressure) (information is provided about the sign language used by criminal groups during the trial, the color of clothing, and behavior), decide on the application of protective measures to other persons participating in the trial³. At the same time, according to the law of the US state of Rhode Island, cases related to ensuring the safety of participants in the process may be considered in the first place at the

¹ Б.Мўминов. Англо-саксон ҳуқуқ тизимида суд назорати. <https://sud.uz/anglo-sakson-huquq-tizimida-sud-nazorati/>.

² Бudyлин С.Л. Внутреннее убеждение или баланс вероятностей? Стандарты доказывания в России и за рубежом // Вестник ВАС РФ. 2014. № 3. С. 25-57.

³ Зайцев О.А. Механизмы обеспечения безопасности свидетелей в Соединенных Штатах Америки // Международное уголовное право и международная юстиция. 2012. № 2. С. 21-23

request of the prosecutor¹. US legislation (Witness Safety Enhancement Act, 1984), like our national criminal procedural legislation, provides for the application of protective measures not only to witnesses and victims, but also establishes the possibility of applying such protective measures to the defendant. However, the state sets certain requirements for the application of protective measures. For example, it is stipulated that a person subject to a state protection measure is required to provide information about the activities of terrorist organizations, organized crime groups, and criminal gangs, even if he or she directly participated in the commission of a crime. However, the evidence provided will be carefully examined. Depending on the level of risk, security measures may be applied to a person (family members, close relatives, and close friends) for a long period of time. In such situations, the following security measures may be applied to persons participating under a pseudonym: non-disclosure of personal information, changing their appearance, changing their address, changing their identification documents, providing them with financial resources, taking measures to exclude surveillance on networks, and so on.

If, during the course of the trial, a request is made by the defense attorney to meet with a witness, and the court finds it necessary to question the persons under protection, the questioning will normally be conducted in the courtroom, and the witness's address will be kept secret from the defense attorney.

Some states (for example, Illinois, California, New York) have adopted their own witness protection programs. These programs provide a much broader list of individuals who are eligible for protection in criminal proceedings. Therefore, this list also includes minors, women, pensioners, the disabled, victims of sexual violence, and police officers².

Criminal liability for disclosing information about victims and witnesses has also been expanded (fines or imprisonment). The mechanism for paying compensation to crime victims has also been improved.

A similar program has been introduced in Canadian law (Witness Protection Program 1996). Each province has a coordinator who is responsible for enrolling witnesses in the program and overseeing its implementation³.

In this regard, the UK has unique legal protections for witnesses. As a basis for the application of protective measures to the participants of the trial, it is used when there is a need to protect the interests of national security, to keep the methods of criminal investigation secret, to protect witnesses from harassment, such as intimidation, rape.

¹ Келли К.М. Запугивание потерпевших и свидетелей. Исследование проблемы и результаты // Зарубежный опыт правового регулирования по вопросам защиты участников уголовного судопроизводства и практика его применения. М., 2000. С. 238-245.

² Брусницын Л. В. Обеспечение безопасности лиц, содействующих... С. 170

³ Witness intimidation: Showdown in the stress — breakdown in the courts: Hearing before the Subcommittee on crime and criminal justice of the Committee on the judiciary, House of representatives one hundred third congress second session, August 4, 1994, Serial № 81. Wash-ington, 1994. — P. 78

If a witness fails to appear in court without a valid reason, the court must determine the validity of the reason for his absence. A valid reason is, in particular, the use of force, intimidation, death or departure abroad by the accused or persons acting in his interests against the witness. If the witness's failure to appear is directly determined by threats from the accused or his representatives, the witness may be exempted from giving evidence in court¹. Such a right can be observed not only in countries belonging to the Anglo-Saxon legal system, but also in countries belonging to the Roman-Germanic family of law. For example, similar provisions are reflected in the criminal procedural legislation of the Netherlands (Article 187 of the Dutch Criminal Procedure Code). We can see similar provisions in Article 68 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Belarus, namely, a victim or witness whose security is ensured may be exempted from appearing in court to give evidence, in which case the judge will read out only the protocols of investigative actions conducted with the participation of persons who have been granted protection measures.

In addition, the judge may request that participants in the trial provide written information about their profile and address in connection with the application of protective measures. The judge also has the right to prohibit the publication in the media of information about persons against whom protective measures have been applied in order to prevent disclosure.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to apply the above rules to national criminal procedural legislation, for this purpose, Article 114, Part 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code *states that if there is reasonable evidence to suggest that the victim, witness, or other participants in the criminal process (family members, close relatives) are being threatened with illegal actions (life, health, property), and the state does not take necessary protective measures for them, the right of the defendant (witness, victim) not to give testimony at the preliminary investigation or trial stage or to limit or completely deprive the defendant of the right to question the witness and participate in the examination of his testimony.*

Thus, the Anglo-Saxon legal system has made it possible to identify positive means of ensuring the safety of a person participating under an alias: including determining the conditions for the expedited consideration of this category of cases by the court; providing information about a specific criminal group to judges in order to apply protective measures to a defendant who is a member of a criminal group; exemption from giving testimony in connection with the unlawful influence exerted on a witness and restrictions on the right of the defendant to ask questions to a witness were considered in detail.

The national legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan has similarities with the Roman-Germanic family of law. In this regard, it is worth comparing the

¹ Брусницын Л.В. Обеспечение безопасности лиц, содействующих уголовному правосудию: мировой опыт и развитие российского законодательства (процессуальное исследование). — М., 2010 — 463 с.

features related to the legal regulation of the security of participants in the criminal process.

Protective measures to ensure the safety of participants in criminal proceedings can be short-term and long-term and are implemented using all methods of protection. According to the law, information about the person against whom protective measures have been taken (place of residence, place of work, public place, courtroom) is protected by the police. These actions help protect the victim, witness not only from illegal influence by the accused or those around him, but also from unforeseen circumstances.

The system of security measures that can be applied in court proceedings is not limited to the procedural means specified in Part 3 of Article 11 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation. The norms of the current Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation regulate the non-disclosure of personal data under a pseudonym in the decision of the judge (court) on the application, change, extension or cancellation of security measures at the stages of the trial or in the content of the verdict. That is, the decision to ensure the security of a participant in the proceedings can be discussed by the court even if the criminal case is terminated. It should be emphasized that judicial activities related to ensuring the security of individuals are not limited to questioning in closed court sessions or in court sessions without disclosing factual information and in conditions that limit visual control by other participants in the proceedings.

The current Russian criminal procedural legislation provides for the application of procedural security measures both during the preliminary investigation and at the trial stage. In particular, conducting the trial in closed court; conducting the trial in conditions that exclude visual observation of the person under the pseudonym by other participants during the trial (Part 5 of Article 278 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); assigning a pseudonym and removing factual information from the materials of the criminal case (reports, including the protocol of the court session) (Part 9 of Article 166 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); wiretapping of telephone conversations (Part 2 of Article 186 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); conducting the trial in conditions of visual identification of the interrogator (Part 8 of Article 193 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); questioning in court through the video conference system (Part 1 of Article 278 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); to appoint a criminal case for trial (Part 1 of Article 278 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); when making a decision to terminate criminal proceedings (Part 3.1 of Article 227 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation).

From the point of view of ensuring the safety of persons in criminal proceedings, the criminal procedural legislation of the Republics of Armenia, Moldova, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Kazakhstan is of particular interest.

Since security measures in these countries are regulated by a separate chapter. This chapter establishes the grounds for applying security measures to both persons assisting in the administration of justice and other persons participating in criminal proceedings. In addition, the legislation of these countries also addresses the issue of ensuring security measures in judicial proceedings in separate articles. We present the main distinguishing features of the rules related to the application of security measures in the above-mentioned countries.

Including: consideration of the decision on the imposition of protective measures by the body conducting the criminal case without delay, but no later than 24 hours from the moment of its receipt (*Article 98 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Armenia*); temporary vacating of the common residence or not approaching the victim's residence, regardless of the property belonging to him; forcing the victim to stay away from his place of residence, while ensuring his safety, excluding any eye contact with his children, other dependents; prohibition of any communication with the victim or his children, other dependents, including by telephone, correspondence or other means; prohibition of approaching certain places: the victim's workplace, the place of study of children, other specific places where the protected person goes; restriction of the right to unilaterally dispose of common property; to force to undergo special treatment or counseling programs, if such a need is determined by the court as a means of reducing or eliminating violence; to prohibit the possession and carrying of weapons; to wear an electronic monitoring system (*Article 215 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova*); to protect a judge, a court investigator, people's assessors, a prosecutor, an investigator, an inquiry officer, a defense attorney, an expert, a specialist, a court clerk, a bailiff, as well as their family members and close relatives (*Article 95 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan*); questioning the victim's child in the presence of a psychologist or teacher and recording it on audio and video recordings for subsequent use in court proceedings; on removing the accused from the courtroom during questioning of the victim's child, witness; in circumstances that exclude recognition of the protected person based on voice and external data: dialect, gender, nationality, age, height, physical condition, posture, gait (*Article 78 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Kyrgyz Republic*); conducting a trial without disclosing information about the witness; questioning a witness in court without the presence of the opposing party; reading out the contents of the witness's testimony during the trial (*Article 109 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Turkmenistan*).

Thus, The advantage of the content of the Criminal Procedure Codes of the Republics of Armenia, Moldova, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Kazakhstan is that the institution of ensuring the security of participants in the criminal process is combined into an independent chapter that defines the foundations and mechanisms of ensuring security.

In many developed countries, the system of legislative measures to protect participants in criminal proceedings has been operating for many years with a tendency to expand and improve. Therefore, the mechanism for supporting and protecting such persons is sufficiently developed. It is necessary to constantly analyze foreign experience and implement it in the national legislative system. Thus, there is an opportunity to introduce effective, time-tested norms into national legislation.

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АДВОКАТУРА ТИЗИМИДА ЮРИДИК ФАННИ ҚЎЛЛАШ АМАЛИЁТИ

Ҳар қандай давлат, у демократик ёки тоталитар ёхуд аралаш тизим асосида шаклланган бўлишидан қатъи назар, ўз бошқарув тизимидан келиб чиқадиган ҳуқуқий асосларга таяниб ўз сиёсатини амалга оширади. Ҳуқуқий асослар, яъни пойдеворнинг мустаҳкамлиги эса юридик фаннинг қай даражада ривожланганига боғлиқ. Юридик фан ривожланган давлатларда шахс, жамият ва давлат ўртасидаги муносабатларни ҳуқуқий жиҳатдан тартибга солишнинг асосий йўналишлари унинг конституциясида ўз ифодасини топади.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституциясининг 53-моддасида “Давлат жамиятнинг маданий, илмий ва техникавий ривожланиши ҳақида ғамхўрлик қилади” деб белгиланганлиги барча фанлар қаторида мамлакатимизда юридик фанларни ҳам ривожлантиришга ҳуқуқий асос бўлиб хизмат қилади. Шу боис Ўзбекистонда юридик соҳада салоҳиятли илмий кадрларни етиштириш баробарида ҳуқуқустувор бўлган жамиятни яратиш долзарб масалалардан бири бўлиб қолади.

Кейинги йилларда жамиятимиз аъзолари ва чет эллик мутахассислар томонидан “демократик давлат”, “ҳуқуқий давлат”, “фуқаролик жамияти” ва шу сингари инсон ҳуқуқлари ва эркинликларининг олий даражада таъминланишини англаувчи юридик терминлар қўлланилаётганлигига гувоҳ бўлмоқдамиз. Бундай эзгу ва инсон қадриятини улуғловчи мақсадга эришиш авваламбор мамлакатимизда юридик фанларнинг ҳосиласи бўлган ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиётига боғлиқдир.

Юридик фанларда ёритиладиган қарашлар, нуқтаи-назарлар ва ғоялар пировардида қабул қилинадиган ҳуқуқий нормаларнинг мазмун-моҳиятида акс этади. Шунингдек, амалдаги норма ижодкорлиги ва ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиёти ўз навбатида юридик фаннинг долзарб масалаларини белгилаб, янгидан-янги илмий йўналишларга туртки беради.

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Олий аттестация комиссияси Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академиясининг (22.10.2024 й., №30/5-153905/24) мурожаатига кўра Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси ташкил этилганлигининг икки йиллиги муносабати билан 2024 йил 21-22 ноябрь кунлари ўтказиладиган **“Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасида глобал чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар: муаммо ва ечимлар”** мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция илмий тўпламида чоп этилган хорижий тиллардаги мақолалар диссертациялар асосий илмий натижаларини чоп этиш тавсия этилган илмий нашрлар рўйхатига киритилган хорижий илмий нашрларда чоп этилган илмий мақолаларга тенглаштирилганлигини маълум қилади.

Асос: ОАК юридик фанлар бўйича эксперт кенгашининг тавсияси (25.10.2024 й., №10); ОАК Тартиб-қонда комиссияси қарори (30.10.2024 й., №10/24); ОАК Раёсати қарори (31.10.2024 й., №363/6).

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